

UDC 377.5

**SYNERGISTIC APPROACH TO THE FORMATION OF A COLLECTIVE
PEDAGOGICAL SUBJECT IN THE SYSTEM OF SECONDARY VOCATIONAL
EDUCATION**

BEGIDOVA SVETLANA NIKOLAEVNA

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor, Adyghe State University,
Maikop, Russia.

Abstract. *The article considers the synergistic approach as a methodological basis for the formation of a collective pedagogical subject in the system of vocational education. The collective pedagogical subject is presented as an open dissipative system, which has seven stages of self-organization: multivariability, chaos, randomness, bifurcation, dissipation, order out of chaos, point of attraction. The key management mechanisms are three synergistic concepts: emergence (the emergence of properties not inherent in individual participants), attractors (points of attraction forming stable development trajectories), and entropy management (balance between order and chaos). The potential of the synergistic approach is realized through four interrelated functions: system-organizational, process-dynamic, activity-practical, and result-productive. The synergistic approach to the formation of a collective pedagogical subject has eight levels of unity (psychological, pedagogical, self-management, intellectual, volitional, organizational, value-based, ideological), which ensures a transition from mechanical control to accompanying the self-organization of the team. The formation of a collective pedagogical subject based on the synergistic approach ensures the effectiveness of this process, increases the stability of the pedagogical team in conditions of transformation of the educational environment.*

Keywords: *synergetics, collective pedagogical subject, resource potential, self-organization, attractor, emergence, entropy.*

The modern educational environment of Secondary Vocational Education (SVE) is characterized by high dynamics, uncertainty, and non-equilibrium. Under such conditions, the pedagogical team ceases to function as a static closed system and requires new methodological bases of management. Traditional hierarchical models built on the principles of linear causality and rigid control are unable to ensure the sustainable development of the team under conditions of constant external disturbances [1, 2]. Today, a transformation of the traditional approach to the formation of a pedagogical team from a mechanical paradigm to a synergistic one, based on the principles of self-organization, is necessary. It is the potential of the synergistic approach as a tool for forming a collective pedagogical subject in the SVE system that allows ensuring the effectiveness of this process in modern conditions of functioning of an educational organization.

Synergetics, introduced into scientific circulation by H. Haken, represents a theory of self-organization of complex non-equilibrium systems [3]. In the pedagogical context, it transforms into "pedagogical synergetics" – a field of knowledge that is in the stage of formation and relies on the laws of self-organization of educational systems [4, 5, 6]. According to V.A. Ignatova, the barrier to the introduction of synergistic ideas into practice is traditional pedagogical attitudes and the time gap between the scientific model and its adaptation in the educational environment [7].

Based on the essence of the synergistic approach, the key principles of synergetics applicable to a pedagogical team are: openness of the system (exchange of energy, information, experience with the external environment), cooperativity (coordinated actions of elements), constructive role of randomness, non-linearity of development, dynamic hierarchicity (emergence) [8, 9, 10]. The collective pedagogical subject functions as an open system, constantly exchanging information, energy, and experience with the external environment. Thanks to this exchange, dynamic equilibrium is maintained, the integrity of the team is preserved, and its ability to self-renew is maintained.

Openness is manifested in the formation of a communicative space with "assembly points" – nodes of concentration of ideas and joint activity.

The evolution of a pedagogical team as a self-organizing system goes through seven stages of its formation:

- Multivariability – uniting teachers with common values, creating a favorable psychological climate, involvement in joint activity;
- Chaos – setting pedagogical problems, stimulating self-education, distribution of management functions;
- Randomness – strengthening of fluctuations, spontaneous self-organization (at this stage, the leader's task is to create conditions for stability);
- Bifurcation – a state of instability when a weak influence determines the development trajectory (a critical moment for correcting motives and climate in the team);
- Dissipation – "healing" of the system through rejection of the least organized elements, strengthening the structure;
- Order out of chaos – ordering of projects, introduction of communication tools, development of regulations;
- Point of attraction – formation of a stable attractor through coordination of goals (the absence of an attractor indicates a system crisis) [11].

Revealing the resource potential of the synergistic approach to the formation of a collective subject in SVE, three key mechanisms should be highlighted through which its realization is carried out – these are emergence, attractors, and entropy management.

Emergence ensures the emergence of new qualities of the team not inherent in individual teams of teachers: network interaction generates collective thinking, joint creativity creates a synergistic effect in solving complex tasks.

Attractors act as "points of attraction" forming stable development trajectories. In a pedagogical team, attractors become a common goal, motivation, trust, a sense of belonging to the team, organization. The more teachers share the attractor, the stronger the attractive force.

Entropy management – balancing between order and chaos. Excessive order leads to stagnation, excessive chaos – to disorganization. The optimal strategy of the leader: artificially increase entropy to stimulate innovations (withdrawal from the comfort zone) and reduce it through closed communicative flows to achieve consistency of actions [10, 11].

The synergistic approach to the formation of a collective pedagogical subject in the SVE system integrates eight levels of unity identified by us. The collective pedagogical subject is formed through the development of unity at the following levels: psychological (consistency of emotional states), pedagogical (unified methodological position), self-management (independence in decision-making), intellectual (striving for self-development, professional improvement), volitiona (direction of efforts to overcome obstacles), organizational (interchangeability and efficiency of interaction), value-based (coincidence of estimates in moral and professional spheres), ideological (common ideals in matters of education and socialization of students). Each level is formed through a combination of emergence, attractors, and entropy management [12].

The resource potential of synergetics is systematically realized through four interrelated functions stemming from its essential characteristics, which include:

- System-organizational – ensures the structuring of the collective pedagogical subject as an open dissipative system with stable internal connections and the ability to self-develop. It is manifested in the creation of communicative "assembly points", formation of a hierarchy of subsystems and maintenance of dynamic equilibrium through exchange with the external environment;
- Process-dynamic – ensures the sequential passage of stages of formation of the collective pedagogical subject: from multivariability through chaos and bifurcation to stable order and points of attraction. This function reflects the non-linear, phase nature of the team's development and allows predicting critical points of transformation;

- Activity-practical function integrates the unity of pedagogical, psychological, self-management, volitional, intellectual, organizational, value-based and ideological aspects of team formation. It is realized through the application of emergence (network interaction), attractors (target coordination) and entropy management (balance of chaos and order) in everyday practice;

- Result-productive is manifested in the formation of a holistic collective pedagogical subject with emergent properties exceeding the sum of individual qualities of team members. The result is the team's ability to self-renew, generate innovations and function sustainably under conditions of external disturbances [13].

The highlighted functions do not act in isolation but form a single system: the system-organizational creates structural prerequisites, the process-dynamic ensures their evolution, the activity-practical realizes them in specific conditions, and the result-productive fixes the final effect.

The organization by the pedagogical team is carried out by its leader. The synergistic approach transforms the role of the head of an educational organization from a subject of control to a facilitator of self-organization. His tasks now are:

- creation of "safe chaos" at the bifurcation stage to stimulate innovations;
- identification and strengthening of natural attractors (common goals, values) instead of imposing directives;
- designing communicative spaces with minimal entropy for critically important processes;
- diagnostics of the stage of team development by dominant parameters (chaos/order, determinism/randomness).

The considered approach is especially effective in conditions of digital transformation of SVE, when rigid hierarchies are replaced by network structures, and system stability is ensured not by control, but by the ability to adapt

Thus, the synergistic approach has significant resource potential for the formation of a collective pedagogical subject in the SVE system. Its methodological potential lies in the rethinking of the pedagogical team as an open non-equilibrium system developing through self-organization. The identified stages of CPS formation, key mechanisms (emergence, attractors, entropy) and levels of unity create a holistic management model focused not on control, but on accompanying natural self-organization processes. The result is the formation of a stable collective pedagogical subject with emergent properties exceeding the sum of individual qualities of its members, which ensures the competitiveness of the educational organization in conditions of an unstable external environment.

REFERENCES

1. Bogdanov A. A. Tektology: Universal Organizational Science / A. A. Bogdanov. — M.: Economics, 1989. — 320 p.
2. Stepanov A. A. Chaos-management: concept in the theory of management of the 21st century / A. A. Stepanov, M. V. Savina, I. A. Stepanov // Bulletin of MSPU. Series: Economics. — 2017. — No. 2(12). — P. 22–29.
3. Haken H. Synergetics: Hierarchies, Coherence, Competition / G. Haken. — M.: Mir, 1985. — 286 p.
4. Meretukova Z. K. Synergistic potential of the suggestopedic culture of a school teacher and university lecturer / Z. K. Meretukova, A. R. Chinazirova // Bulletin of Adyghe State University. Ser.: Pedagogy and Psychology. — 2014. — Issue 3 (143). — URL:<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/sinergeticheskiy-potentsial-suggestopediynoy-kultury-uchitelya-shkoly-i-prepodavatelya-vuza> (accessed: 08.07.2024).
5. Talanchuk N. M. Pedagogical synergetics as a basis of innovative education / N. M. Talanchuk // Pedagogy and Modernity. — 2018. — No. 2. — P. 12–19.
6. Kureichik V. M. Pedagogical synergetics: formation of a new field of knowledge / V. M. Kureichik, V. I. Pisarenko // Bulletin of RSUH. Series "Pedagogy". — 2015. — No. 3. — P. 45–52.
7. Ignatova V. A. Synergetics in education: methodological aspects / V. A. Ignatova // Pedagogy. — 2010. — No. 4. — P. 25–31.
8. Haken H. Information and Self-Organization: A Macroscopic Approach to Complex Systems / G. Haken. — M.: Mir, 1991. — 240 p.
9. Prigogine I. R. Order out of chaos. Man's new dialogue with nature / I. R. Prigogine, I. Stengers. — Toronto ; New York : Bantam Books, 1984. — 385 p.
10. Synergy: Powering Success Through Strategic Collaboration. — URL: <https://penpoin.com/Grow-Your-Business/Competitive-strategy> (accessed: 07.06.2025).
11. Zhamalova A. R. Synergistic approach to modeling a personnel attractor in an educational organization / A. R. Zhamalova // Concept: scientific-methodological electronic journal. — 2016. — Special Issue No. 3. — URL: <http://e-koncept.ru/2016/76036.htm> (accessed: 10.08.2023).
12. Serikov V. V. Management of a developing educational system: creation of a collective pedagogical subject / V. V. Serikov // Collective subjects of pedagogical and managerial activity: properties, functions, conditions of formation: materials of the XI International Pedagogical Readings "Collective subjects of pedagogical and managerial activity in cultural-competence and system-activity educational models". — Volgograd: Publishing House of Lyceum No. 8 "Olympia": VGAPK RO, 2012. — P. 21–28.
13. Corning P. A. Synergy and Self-Organization in Human Evolution / P. A. Corning // Proceedings of the 38th Annual Meeting, International Society for the Systems Sciences. — 1994. — P.